

Water balance analysis of the effect of drought on upland rice

S. R. Patel and A. S. R. A. S. Sastri,
Zonal Agricultural Research Station,
Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University,
Raipur, India

In central India, there are about 0.9 million ha of upland rice. Soils are black with 60% clay. Rice yields are 0.3 to 0.6 t/ha.

For better water management, it is important to know the duration and intensity of water stress during different growth stages. We analyzed the water stress pattern resulting from drought during growth stages from 1981 to 1983 based on the ratio of actual evapotranspiration to the potential evapotranspiration (AE:PE) determined by water balance computations. The Purva grain yield for the analysis was from cropping pattern experiments under upland conditions.

The drought period was initiated when the actual AE:PE values fell below optimum, which are 0.75, 1.00, 1.00, 0.50 during seedling, vegetative, reproductive, and maturity stages (see figure).

Drought intensity varied in the first three growth stages. It was highest (more hatched area) in 1982 followed by 1981; yields were 0.9 and 1.0 t/ha. In 1983, mild drought occurred at vegetative and reproductive stages and rice yielded 1.3 t/ha.

Drought during different physiological stages of upland rice Raipur, India.

This suggests that under upland conditions in central India, rice production without a suitable water harvesting or soil

water conservation practice is not practical. □

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Deep water rice and fish culture

S. K. Datta, D. Konar, S. K. De, P. K. Banerjee, Operational Research Project (ORP), Pandua, West Bengal; and P. K. Pandit, Central Inland Fisheries Research Institute, Barrackpore, West Bengal, India

We evaluated an integrated system of deep water rice and fish culture followed by lowland rice culture to increase farm productivity at ORP, West Bengal.

A 0.2-ha renovated, 2.5-m-deep plot

for deep water rice cultivation was constructed with a 12 × 8 × 1.5 m central tank. Soil was a clay loam with pH 7.0-7.5. The tank was thoroughly plowed, 10 t farmyard manure/ha was incorporated, and Jaladhi 1, a recommended deep water rice, was direct-seeded in early Jun 1983. Standard cultivation was practiced. Water depth reached a maximum 160 cm and varied as shown in Figure 1.

In late Jul, carp fingerlings - silver carp *Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*, Mrigal *Cirrhinus mrigala*, Catla *Catla catla*,

and Rohu *Labeo rohita* — were released in the plot at 9,000/ha in the ratio 6:6:1:1. Each morning, they were fed an inexpensive 1:1 mixture of rice bran and oil cake at 5% total body weight.

In late Dec, mature rice panicles were harvested and fish were harvested periodically by drag net. Only 75% of the fish were table-sized in the first harvest (Fig. 2). The plot was allowed to dry gradually and the remaining small fish were moved to the central tank where they were fed regularly. Final fish harvest was in late Feb.